
HALLOWED LIFE ON THE GREAT GOAL TRAIL

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Xalqaro huquq va qiyosiy huquqshunoslik

Annotation in English.

this article talks about the career path of Khadichha Sulaimanova, the first female scholar of the great Uzbek jurisprudence.

Keywords in English.

Khadicha Sulaimanova, former union, first, law, court.

Annotation in Uzbek.

mazkur maqolada buyuk o'zbek huquqshunoslik fanining ilk ayol darg'asi bo'lgan Xadicha Sulaymonovaning faoliyat yo'li haqida so'z boradi.

Keywords in Uzbek.

Xadicha Sulaymonova, Sobiq Ittifoq, ilk, huquq, sud.

Annotation in Russian.

в данной статье рассказывается о творческом пути Хадичхи Сулаймановой, первой женщины-ученого великой узбекской юриспруденции.

Keywords in Russian.

Хадича Сулайманова, бывший Союз, во-первых, закон, суд.

In the world, the concept of society appears, in which the main factor is considered a person. Even at all times, the Society of man is confused about the human Earth, its rights, moral standards. Whether it be religious or secular views, there will be attempts to form a person, thereby changing the being.

Issues such as centuries-old problems, social stratification, grouping, and the discovery of human dignity remain a painful point of human society. In particular, the leader was the discrimination of the prestige of women in society, looking at her from among the paws as a person.

After Uzbekistan achieved independence, significant changes began to take place on all fronts. As a confirmation of this, the concept of Gender equality began to be put forward. Unprocessed chalk is unlikely to change even on facades that do not have a certain root, which does not have a certain root, where the first steps are taken and the foundation stones are not laid. When we pay attention to the history

of the nation, our women were very involved in collective farms and other domestic affairs. It is known to us that among the Uzbek women, the first mechanizers, and growers, a number of people grew up in other aspects of the whitening sphere, but women who defended human dignity, its moral, and legal values, were practically immature. It was Khadicha Sulaymanova, a vehement Uzbek woman who took on such a difficult, heavy, threatening burden from the point of view of that time. Referring to this name, we can witness many times the concepts of the first, the first when we look at the history of his life, and this definition of the first was used not only for Uzbekistan but in certain respects for a woman who was the first for the whole world, the world.

Remembering the great defender of human rights, Khadija Suleymanova's Memorial Night was held for the first time in January 1991 at the Institute of Philosophy and Law of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In memory of the bright memory of our great ancestor, the path of heavy, but contented activity that she traversed was remembered as a lesson

Khadicha Sulaymanova was one of the first jurist cadres in the Soviet Socialistic Republic of Uzbekistan, graduating from the Institute of Soviet Construction and law in the September of 1935. It is not difficult to imagine how much a difficult task our ancestor had as a person: first, a positive system, on the second hand, a people in the victim, on the third, a society in which the right of women was discriminated against... working in such conditions, living life itself was a heroism.

Khadija Sulaymanova began her career as a people's judge after graduating from the Institute, which brought her closer to the people. Although there is still no concept of a people's judge, itinerant courts have been set up to solve the problems of the masses on the spot. In late 1935, he was elected to the Supreme Court of the Republic. The fact that a twenty-two-year-old woman achieved such a high rank was supposedly a mirage for every member of our nation. This was the youngest member of the Supreme Court to date, compared not only to women but also to men. Sulaymanova presided over the most serious and seriously considered criminal cases for that time in such a threatening period.

At the time of the Muslim regime, history and legal literature were formed in a revolutionary spirit. The first Uzbek woman to cover the criminal law and punitive policy of this period on a scientific basis is Khadija Sulaymanova. As an early swallow, the only work done as an Apple was not the only one, Khadija Sulaymanova created the history of criminal law and court of the Soviet Socialistic

Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of the study of many normative acts and acts, literature of the era of the Soviet Union, is also of great importance as the first person to create the general laws

In his research, Sulaymanova paid special attention to the issue of the construction of socialism and the improvement of criminal law in Uzbekistan during the victory of socialism. In addition, she gave a perfect description of the Criminal Code of the first Uzbek SSR, which entered into force in June 1926. He is also one of the authors and editor of the textbook on criminal law in Uzbekistan, which was first published in the Uzbek language. This textbook was developed precisely as a guide on the initiative of Khadija Sulaymanova. It is also noteworthy that he created more than 80 works for the purpose of developing the field of law.

Khadija Sulaymanova's published work is usually characterized by the relevance of the chosen topic, bold rise and illumination of important theoretical problems, substantiation of advanced requirements, scientific generalizations, and the issuance of conclusions on the basis of clear evidence. The sameness of each work done, and its focus on concrete results, caused him to be especially recognized both as a nobleman and as a skillful connoisseur and practitioner of his work. As a result of this, he was awarded by the Supreme Soviet Presidium the honorary title of "scientist who showed service in the Uzbek SSR", the "Order of the Mark of honor", the medal "for Gallant labor during the Great Patriotic War".

On his initiative, The Collegian discussion included not only practical issues but also theoretical issues related to the correct application of the norms of material and procedural law on controversial issues of somewhat complex work, theft of property of socialism, payment of benefits, etc.

The fact that Khadija Sulaymanova also carried out some previous issues in the name of her homeland with the world society further increases the sense of respect and admiration for her. In February 1959, a very important event was held in Tashkent - an inter-Republican scientific conference with the participation of Representatives of the Uzbek SSR, Kazakh SSR, Kyrgyz SSR, Tajik SSR, and Turkmen SSR, dedicated to the codification of laws. Representatives of the Justice bodies of the Union of the SSR, the republics of Central Asia, jurist scientists from Moscow, Leningrad, the Allied republics, as well as party and Soviet employees took part in the conflict. This is considered the first major convention of scholar and practitioner jurisprudence in Tashkent, and one of the initiators and leaders of the confessional, which was organized for the first time, is Khadija Sulaymanova. In January 1961, she was also one of the first participants in the first Asian and African

Women's Congress, held in Cairo, the capital of the United Arab Republic. Khadicha Sulaymanova, acting as a representative of the Women's Council of the republics of the Soviet East, spoke on behalf of the Soviet delegation at this conference of Asian and African women passing for the first time in history, congratulated the participants of the conference, thanked the people of the United Arab Republic for the care given to women from the Soviet Union.

Khadicha Sulaymanova, the pride, pride of the nation, was also the first Uzbek doctor, Professor, and academician in the field of Legal Sciences. Looking at the history of Uzbek jurisprudence, Khadija Sulaymanova, the only academic Apple that matured from this branch of the former Union era, has grown a number of vehement, not only Uzbek, but also disciples who have a place in the field of World jurisprudence during her academic career. Both during his tenure as head of the department and during his time as a faculty, and throughout his life, he was apprenticed to him, with the support of which we can meet many prominent figures who made significant contributions to the life of society and the state in favor of doctoring dissertations. They also the following points, recognizing that Khadija Sulaymanova was one of the first. Below we decided to cite the points expressed by the disciples in a way of pride:

1."In 1956, Khadicha Sulaymanova became a real member of the Academy of Sciences on the basis of a majority vote by holding a secret election at the General Assembly of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, until then no one had such a supreme title from within women," writes Sabohat Azimzhonova.

2." In the history of the culture of our republic, in the emergence and development of the science of our Republic, one usually speaks specifically of the first. Khadicha Sulaymanova is among the first of these. Khadicha Sulaymanova is one of the founders of legal doctrine in Uzbekistan, one of the organizers of law enforcement agencies," said Dr. Anvar Azamkhojayev.

3. In the 50s, there were very few doctors of science in our republic, especially from Uzbeks, and there were 20-25 people. The first and only doctor of science in social sciences from Uzbek women was Khadicha Sulaymanova. Khadicha Sulaymanova, despite her still young age, was famous as a mature apple not only in the Republic but also throughout the world. Khadija Suleymanova was a bright star that came out of Uzbek women, " Abdulhai Valiyev said.

We want to end our thought with a short but correct definition of Khadicha Sulaymonova, i.e.: man is dead when he is alive, and man is alive when he died.

Even though Khadija Sulaymanova has lost her life and she is still alive through her noble deeds, despite the fact that more than a century has passed since.

LITERATURE USED:

1. "Khadicha Suleymanova lawyer, scientist, statesman". Khakimov. G', Akhmedov.A, Saidov.T Uzbekistan, 1993.-151b.
2. "Academic Khadija". Malik hakimovich Hakimov. Uzbekistan. -1974.